

FOOD PROCESSING ISSUES

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Annotation: Agriculture is the main source of raw materials for the growth of the gross domestic product and ensuring food security. The article describes the need to obtain food products by processing agricultural products. Some problems in the field of food processing are indicated. Also, the volume of food products produced in the Namangan region in the last year was analyzed, relevant conclusions were given.

Key words: food industry, processing, storage of cultivated products, shelf life, ensuring food safety, food waste, beverage production, development of processing technologies

INTRODUCTION

The food industry is an important component of our country's economy, and in that sector, goods are created that satisfy the primary needs of the population and ensure the security of our country.

Special attention is paid to the development of infrastructure for deep processing of agricultural raw materials and storage of cultivated products. Some of the food products grown in agriculture are processed on an industrial basis in order to extend their shelf life and maintain their quality and usefulness. In agriculture, many types of food products useful for humans are grown and processed on an industrial basis. Some of the food products grown in our republic are also exported to foreign countries.

As the President noted: "The land of Uzbekistan has long been famous for its ancient and rich agricultural traditions, extremely diverse, delicious and unique agricultural products"

We pay special attention to the issues of turning agriculture into a more efficient and resource-saving sector in our country, improving the living standards of rural residents, providing our people with safe and vitamin-rich food products at affordable and stable prices, and establishing a healthy diet" [1].

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Consequently, in recent years, the approach to ensuring food safety, increasing the quality of agricultural products and export potential in our country has completely changed, and it has been turned into a priority direction of state policy. This means that the topic is relevant.

Main part

It is known that the food industry in the world plays an important role in meeting the nutritional needs of people. At the same time, it also faces the problem of excessive food waste.

First, processed food has a significant environmental footprint. The process of food production has negative impacts on the environment, from fertile soil and fresh water resources to the energy costs of food production and transportation. When food waste is sent to landfill, it decomposes and releases methane, one of the main greenhouse gases that contribute to climate change. Food waste recycling helps reduce the environmental problems associated with food waste storage and decomposition.

Second, processed food has the potential to solve hunger and malnutrition in many parts of the world. While millions of people suffer from food insecurity, large amounts of processed food are wasted every day. If these foods could be processed and used as food, it would be possible to reduce the level of hunger and reduce the demand for new food production.

In addition, processed food can be a source of fresh products and ingredients. Food waste processing technologies such as biotechnology and composting can turn waste into valuable resources. For example, processed products can be used as fertilizers or components for biogas production. This approach helps reduce dependence on limited resources and promotes sustainable development [9].

Therefore, processing of food products and delivering it to consumers is one of the most pressing issues. Measures for the development of agro-industry are being implemented in the Namangan region in order to provide the population with quality agricultural products, to extend their shelf life, and to prevent them from perishing.

In Namangan region, taking into account the soil and climate conditions of the regions, specialization in horticulture, viticulture, vegetable-polishing, potato, leguminous and oil crops cultivation, as well as goat breeding, beekeeping and fishing, as well as increasing the production of competitive products and producing agricultural products in order to increase the interest of subjects, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 303 of May 17, 2021 “On

measures to increase the volume of agricultural products by developing the specialization of regions in the Namangan region” was adopted.

It envisages taking measures to implement the following measures together with the relevant ministries and agencies of the Namangan region administration:

- development and re-use of land areas based on measures determined in 2021;
 - ensuring the allocation of funds required for the construction, construction, installation of equipment and equipment of irrigation networks (water pumps, wells, collectors, electrical networks, etc.) and their intended use;
 - effective use of available land areas and water resources, planting of crops in integrated areas in order to increase the volume of production, processing and export, and ensuring at least 2-3 harvests from the specified exportable processing enterprises, cold warehouses and logistics centers will be fully operational during 2021-2022 and ensure their operation at full capacity;
 - based on the available opportunities in the regions, establishment of farms specializing in vegetable crops and seed potatoes, as well as fruit tree and vine seedlings;
 - starting from March 1, 2024, in the districts specializing in lemon cultivation, ensure the sale of plots of land for lemon cultivation at the expense of unused and pasture land for electronic online auctions;
 - establishing greenhouse farms specializing in lemon growing and supplying them with the required natural gas in an established manner;
- such as the development of the goat breeding network with effective use of pasture lands in the region and the introduction of a system of industrial processing of raw goat leather and wool.
- In order to ensure the fulfillment of the above tasks, we will refer to specific indicators. If we analyze the indicators of industrial production in Namangan region in recent years, the volume of industrial products processed by industrial enterprises

Table 1

Production of industrial products by types of economic

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Types of activities	Billion soums	Share in %
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Manufacturing industry	16 951,8	100,0
Food production	2 968,2	17,5
Beverage production	772,4	4,5
Production of tobacco products	0,0	0,0

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In terms of regions, the highest share of food production in the total volume of the

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Table 2

Production volume and growth rate of food products

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The name of the regions	Volume, billion soum	Share of the total, in %	compared to January-December 2022, in %
Total by province	3 191,8	100,0	98,5
Namangan city	1 614,6	50,6	112,3
Mingbulak	60,3	1,9	84,2
Kasansay	78,9	2,5	73,2
Namangan district	193,2	6,1	75,7
Narin	64,0	2,0	104,9
Pap	168,6	5,3	80,7
Turakurgan	65,2	2,0	98,9
Uychi	211,2	6,6	141,5
Uchkurgan	180,3	5,6	53,5
Chartak	345,4	10,8	130,4
Chust	99,3	3,1	90,8
Yangikurgan	110,8	3,5	64,3

However, some challenges must be overcome to implement complete food processing. First of all, it is necessary to activate the awareness and formation of society about food waste problems and possible ways to solve them. Government agencies, community organizations, and the food industry can work together to

develop effective systems for the collection, processing, and distribution of processed food.

Another important aspect is the development of food waste processing technologies. Innovations in biotechnology, composting and other processing methods allow more efficient use of waste, creating new products and materials. Research and investment in these areas will help develop sustainable and cost-effective solutions.

There are also some other problems in this area - problems in the development of export of products [2,5,6], unsatisfactory communications in the provision of information [3], slowness in the development and application of innovations [4], problems in the use of digital technologies [7,8].

Conclusions

Food processing is a production process that transforms agricultural products into food products. The food industry includes many forms of food processing, for example, from the simplest grinding of grain to obtain flour, to the preparation of ready meals in complex industrial conditions.

The advantages of organizing processing enterprises can be seen in the following: the perishability of agricultural products is put to an end, the assortment of agricultural products increases, the shelf life is extended, as a result of primary and secondary processing of food products additional added value is obtained; additional opportunities for exporting products will be created; import substitution becomes possible; appropriate infrastructure will be developed; additional jobs will be created. In summary, processed food represents an important aspect of the modern food industry. It has significant environmental and social potential, but also presents challenges that require collective efforts and innovation. Through more efficient food waste processing and management systems, we can reduce our impact on the environment, reduce hunger and create a more sustainable society based on the efficient use of food resources.

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